

CRACK ADVANCEMENT IN A CARBON FIBRE-EPOXY COMPOSITE
OBSERVED BY DYNAMIC SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

Instrumented tensile tests of double edge notched carbon fibre-epoxy specimens were performed inside the vacuum chamber of a scanning electron microscope. The formation of damage at the notch tip was observed and its effect on laminate strength was measured for a variety of cross-ply lay-ups. Of all the damage processes observed, splitting in the 0° plies was found to have the greatest influence on laminate strength.

INTRODUCTION

The distinction between the notched strength and toughness of fibre composites is often confused because of the complex ways in which these materials fail. In a monotonic tensile test, crack growth is accompanied by the formation of large damage zones at the crack tip. These zones may contain interlaminar failure (delamination), intralaminar failure (splitting), fibre debonding, pullout and fracture. The study of such a complex failure process has inevitably led to the development of simplified failure models [1-5].

Although reasonably successful in predicting experimental notched tensile strengths, these models give no understanding of the mechanics of crack advance. Consequently, the models do not provide a physical basis for describing the notch sensitivity effect. Of particular concern is that many of the models are based on a localised stress distribution predicted using the initial sample and notch geometry [5]. In many laminates, however, the 0° plies split extensively during loading [6-8], changing the

stress distribution ahead of the notch [9]. In fact, the failure stress must depend uniquely on the terminal damage state and the resulting modified stress distribution.

In the present study, crack tip damage accumulation in a carbon fibre-epoxy composite has been observed in real time in a scanning electron microscope. This approach yields insight into the influence of crack tip damage on the strength of notched composite materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Previous fractographic studies of fibrous composites using the SEM have been primarily confined to "post mortems" [10-12]. In this study, cross-plyed carbon fibre-epoxy laminates were fractured during SEM observation using a miniature, fully instrumented tensile rig. The equipment is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of SEM tension rig.

The cross-head was driven by a stepper motor connected through a 100-1 reduction worm gear. Pulses from a BBC-B microcomputer were used to drive the motor, each pulse resulting in $0.03 \mu\text{m}$ of cross-head displacement. The rig was fitted with a 5 kN load cell and a clip gauge mounted between opposing wedge grip faces to measure true cross-head displacement.

Readings of load and displacement were datalogged by the BBC microcomputer through onboard A/D converters. Periodic measurements of crack tip opening displacement were possible using the image magnification calibration of the Cambridge Instruments Stereoscan 200 SEM.

The controlling program allowed the user to pause the loading and insert comments at any point in the data file. The data file was stored on disk for subsequent analysis. For each test, a load/displacement curve was plotted on an x-y plotter, and the locations of loading pauses were marked with vertical lines on the plot.

The video image from the SEM was recorded onto videotape and subsequently enhanced with a recursive filtering system [13]. This system displays an image which represents the average of an adjustable number of frames, providing a very high signal to noise ratio. Because the filtering system is digital, photographs are limited in resolution by the resolution of the display monitor.

The material tested was cross-ply 914C/T300 carbon fibre-epoxy laminate manufactured by DFVLR. Double edged notched (DEN) specimens measuring 8.4 mm x 5 mm were machined to size with an endmill. A 45° cutting wheel was used to mill a notch 1.25 mm deep on opposing edges of the coupon yielding a notch length to specimen width ratio, $2a/W$, of 0.5 for all specimens.

Some of the specimens were tested on an Instron 1195 equipped with a 5 kN load cell. Other specimens were tested in the SEM chamber using the miniature rig. The tensile strengths reported represent an average of at least four samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 is a typical load/displacement curve produced by the plotter. The materials were generally elastic to failure, although some specimens exhibited a decrease in stiffness near the failure load. The load drops at displacements of 0.25 mm and 0.3 mm (fig. 2) correspond to relaxation of the sample and the grips during pauses in loading. The length and location of each pause were printed separately.

The linearity of the plots indicates that little energy was absorbed by the progressive damage which accumulated near the notch tip. Transverse ply cracks, delaminations, splits and fibre breaks initiated and propagated throughout the test, and were clearly visible on the SEM monitor (fig. 3,5,6).

In general, however, it was not possible to attribute stiffness changes to individual damage processes.

Figure 2. Typical load/displacement plot from SEM tensile test.

Figure 3. Splitting in a $(0)_4$ laminate.
(scale bar = 200 μm)

The mechanism of 0° splitting is clearly illustrated in figure 3. In this photograph, the original notch root is marked by a line of machining debris. Cracks have propagated perpendicular to the starter notch direction, parallel to the 0° fibres, in both directions from the notch tip. The notch was effectively blunted by this mechanism, and the ligament stress at the notch tip was decreased with increasing split length [9]. Extensive splitting may explain the notch shape insensitivity of many composites.

A series of $(90/0_n/90)$ laminates, where $n = 1, 2, 4$, were tested to examine the effect of the terminal damage state (TDS) on laminate strength. In this study, TDS is characterized by the 0° split length only, although in principle, all forms of damage could influence the terminal stress distribution at the tip of the notch.

The normalised laminate strengths are presented in figure 4. The normalised strength is the failure load divided by the ligament area of the 0° plies only. This method of plotting is based on the assumption that all of the load at failure is carried by the 0° fibres. As shown in figure 4, a thicker central ply led to an increase in laminate strength.

Figure 4. Strength data for laminae with central plies of varying thickness. Normalised strength is $(P_{ult})/(\text{area of } 0^\circ \text{ plies in ligament})$.

a) (90/0/90)

b) (90/0₂/90)

c) (90/0₄/90)

Figure 5. Damage at the tip of the notch at 100% of the failure load.
(scale bar = 200 μm)

Figures 5a-c depict the notch tip damage prior to failure. The 0° fibres in each case were exposed by the splitting mechanism previously described. The crack tip opening displacement (CTOD) is assumed to be proportional to the split length, although this relationship must depend on the constraining forces imposed by the 90° plies. The laminates displayed

a) $(90/0)_{2s}$ $\sigma_n = 1398 \pm 90$ MPa

b) $(90_2/0_2)_s$ $\sigma_n = 1764 \pm 70$ MPa

Figure 6. Damage at the tip of the notch at 100% of the failure load.
 (scale bar = 200 μm) σ_n = normalised stress

different terminal damage states because of the differing degrees of constraint on the central ply. The reduced stress concentration at the notch tip caused by longer splits has apparently led to a higher strength for the laminates with thicker central 0° plies. This is supported by the fact that the (90/0/90) laminates all failed within 0.5 mm of the machined notch tip, while the 0° central plies of the thicker laminates failed as much as 5 mm away from the notch tip.

The effect of constraint on terminal damage is illustrated with two similar lay-ups in figure 6. In the $(90/0)_{2s}$ laminate, the 0° plies were highly constrained and 0° ply splitting was inhibited. Since the notch was not substantially blunted, the specimens failed near the notch tip where the concentrated stress was a maximum. The longer splits in the $(90_2/0_2)_s$ laminates, as indicated by the increased CTOD measurement, reduced the tensile stress on the 0° fibres in the neighbourhood of the blunted notch tip. The 0° plies of this laminate failed away from the notch tip at a relatively high stress.

Few studies have considered the crack blunting effect, even though notch shape insensitivity is well documented [14]. These studies do not, in general, treat the terminal damage as an important variable in the determination of laminate strength. When the terminal stress distribution for each sample is known, the task of relating this distribution to failure strength should be greatly simplified.

CONCLUSIONS

The notched tensile strength of carbon fibre-epoxy is dependent on the lay-up of the laminate. This dependence can be attributed to a modification of the terminal stress distribution at the notch tip by damage accumulation which is unique for each lay-up. A complete approach to the modelling of notched composite strength must therefore incorporate the effect of notch tip damage on the localised stress in the load bearing plies. Dynamic scanning electron microscopy can provide some critical information about this damage.

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